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The set of genes that defines that human embryonic stem cell identity.

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Here we utilized genomic methods to compare total transcription in fibroblasts and embryonic stem cells. We also studied the most significant changes in the ES cell transcriptome using hematopoietic stem cells (CD34+ HSCs) and human ES cells (H1 and H9). Our discovery approach included *de novo* isolation and identification of nuclear factors, membrane receptors and other genes that uniquely characterized the embryonic stem cell. We describe here, among other major components of the human embryonic stem cell, expression of the developmental complexes lin-28a and lin-28b.